

Root CEC was significantly reduced under sodic conditions (Table 1). Reduction was least in IR8, followed by Pokkali and Jaya. IR8 also had less reduction in plant height, root length, shoot weight, and grain weight.

Pusa 2-21 was tolerant of alkalinity, in terms of reduction in root CEC under sodic conditions, and performed better in terms of plant height, shoot weight, and grain weight (Table 2). CSSR3 and Damodar, with the lowest root CEC, performed poorly in terms of shoot weight, grain test weight, plant height, and root length. □

Table 2. Yield-contributing parameters of rice varieties in normal and alkali soils. Kanpur, India.

Variety	Plant height (cm)		Fresh wt of shoot/plant (g)		1000-grain wt (g)	
	Normal	Alkali	Normal	Alkali	Normal	Alkali
IR8	63	55	62.82	55.54	22.650	22.620
Jaya	70	51	95.03	60.02	24.600	22.686
M1-48	107	93	150.15	102.83	26.640	23.645
Pokkali	104	89	145.52	84.36	28.240	24.800
Pusa 2-21	79	75	44.26	40.85	19.940	19.180
Damodar	77	63	138.71	83.91	21.244	14.586
Saket 4	71	66	92.54	64.32	26.600	24.110
CSSR3	73	71	204.69	146.36	19.080	17.240
LSD (0.05)	3	3	2.88	2.39	1.018	0.983

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

OM80, a high-yielding rice variety released in Vietnam

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OM80, a 1983 selection from the cross IR5853/NN3A in the high-yielding rice variety breeding program at CLRRI, was advanced to adaptive farmers' field trials in 1986. OM80 maintained its superior performance at all test locations, averaging 6 t/ha in 1986 (see table).

It was approved by the Standing Seed Board of the Ministry of Agricul-

Yield and disease and insect resistance of OM80 tested at CLRRI, Omon, Haugiang, Vietnam, 1986.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Reaction ^a to			
		BPH	B1	BB	ShB
OM80	6.1	3-5	3-5	7	7
NN6A (check)	5.2	3	7-9	7	7
CV (%)	20.4				
LSD (0.05)	0.6				

^a By the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale in artificial screening condition at CLRRI in 1986.

ture and released for large-scale cultivation in the Mekong River delta in 1987 and in the Hong River delta in 1989.

OM80 has 115-120 d duration, is 95-100 cm high, and has a high number of effective tillers. It was found to be

tolerant of slight-medium acid sulfate soils, moderately resistant to blast (B1) and brown planthopper (BPH) biotype 2, and susceptible to bacterial blight (BB) and sheath blight (ShB). The superior feature of OM80 is high yields at low fertilizer inputs. □

TM2011, a short-duration fine rice in Tamil Nadu

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We tested several cultivars with high yield potential and pest and disease resistance for five seasons—dry (rabi) 1986, 1987 1988 and early wet (kharif) 1987, 1988—in a randomized block design with three replications. TM2011 performed well.

TM2011 is a hybrid derivative of C22/TKM6//IR50 with 112-d duration,

76.40 cm plant height, and seven reproductive tillers per plant. Grain yield was 1.46-12.64% higher than that of IR50 (Table 1).

The culture was advanced to multilocation trials in 1988 wet season. At Bhavanisagar, Pondicherry, and Tirur, TM2011 gave 6.6-9.6% higher yields than IR50.

In screening for pest resistance at Tirur, TM2011 was resistant to leaf-folder and green leafhopper and moderately resistant to gall midge and stem borer.

Screening results in Coimbatore, Aduthurai, Madurai, and Amba-

Table 1. Grain yield of TM2011. ^a RRS, Tirur, Tamil Nadu, India, 1986-88.

Season	Year	Grain yield (t/ha)		Difference (%)
		TM2011	IR50	
Dry	1986	4.6 (116)	4.6 (118)	101
Dry	1987	4.6 (115)	4.2 (110)	109
Early wet	1987	5.8 (108)	5.6 (110)	104
Dry	1988	4.7 (110)	4.2 (108)	113
Early wet	1988	4.6 (110)	4.2 (105)	111

^a Figures in parentheses are crop duration, in days.

samudram are presented in Table 2.

In varietal trials in the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project during 1984 kharif, TM2011